

Scelionidae [*Telenomus cirphivorus* Liu.], and Carabidae [*Calathus halensis* Schall., *Calosoma maderae chinense* Kirby].

Seasonal migration in eastern China was traced by releasing and recapturing marked moths. Results indicate that the moth is a regular immigrant from the southern provinces to the northeast in early spring. A return migration takes place in late summer or fall.

The maize armyworm *Mythimna loreyi* Duponchel is found in Chekiang, Kiangsu, Kwangtung, Kwangsi, Fukien, Hunan, Hupeh, Szechuan, Kweichow, Kiangsi, Taiwan, and Ginsu Provinces. In Kwangtung, it damages rice in June-July by feeding on the leaves and cutting the spikelets. Parasites of *M. loreyi* include Tachinidae [*Cuphocera varia* Fabricius, *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wied.)], Braconidae [*Apanteles* sp.], and Ichneumonidae [*Enicospilus* sp.].

The grain armyworm *Mythimna compta* (Moore) is found in Hupeh, Hunan, Kiangsi, Yunan, Fukien, Chekiang, Kweichow, Kwangtung, and Kwangsi Provinces. In Fukien, it causes significant injury in June-July during its second generation and serious damage in October-November during its fifth generation. In Kwangtung, its infestation on rice is lighter than other species.

The millet armyworm *Mythimna zea* (Duponchel) infests wheat, millet, and rice in Sinkiang Province in the west-northern part of China. It produces two generations a year and the full-grown larva hibernates in the soil. The first generation in June-July causes significant damage.

The nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia* Boisduval is found in Kiangsu, Hupeh, Kiangsi, Kwangsi, Kwangtung, Taiwan, and Fukien Provinces. Caterpil-

lars of the 5th generation attack rice severely in Kwangtung in July-August. It often occurs in rice fields that are easily flooded. An outbreak is closely related to water in the fields.

The small nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera abyssinia* Guenée occurs in Hunan, Fukien, Kwangsi, and Kwangtung Provinces. The caterpillars infest rice seedlings during the second season in June-July in Kwangtung. The duration of the summer generation lasts about 33 days in Guangzhou.

The green nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera depravata* (Butler) is found in Giling, Shensi, Hupeh, Kiangsi, Szechuan, Chekiang, Kiangsu, Fukien, and Kwangtung Provinces.

The striped nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera pecten* Guenée occasionally infests rice in Fukien, Kwangtung, and Kwangsi Provinces. ■

Weed hosts of some rice pests in North Western Sierra Leone

A. M. Alghali and J. S. Domingo, Rice Research Station, Rokupr, Sierra Leone

Grasses in the rice fields of associated tidal mangrove swamps of Mawirr and Magbolontor and the mangrove swamp of the Rice Research Station in Rokupr, Kambi District, North Western Sierra Leone, were examined for adults, eggs, larvae, and nymphs of rice insect pests (see table). Insects at immature stages were reared to adults for identification. ■

Distribution of some rice insects on weeds in North Western Sierra Leone.

Insect	Insect stage	Site	Weed host	Rice crop stage
<i>Diopsis thoracica</i> West.	Eggs and adults	Mawirr	<i>Rottboellia exaltata</i> L.f.	Heading
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i> Melichar	Nymphs	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
			<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Heading
<i>Herpetogramma licarsialis</i> Walk.	Larvae	Rokupr mangrove swamp	<i>Paspalum vaginatum</i> Swartz	Vegetative
		Mawirr	<i>I. rugosum</i>	Heading
<i>Epilachna similis</i> Muls.	Nymphs and adults	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
<i>Pteronemobius</i> sp.	Eggs	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp.	Feeding lesions	Mange	<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schumach.	Heading

Life span and tungro transmission of viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens*

Dara Chettanachit and Somkid Disthaporn, Rice Pathology Branch, Division of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 9, Thailand

The rice tungro virus Collaborative Project investigated the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens*. In two trials in Thailand, 80 adult insects—40 females and 40 males—each for 10 varieties were given 4 days

access on tungro-diseased plants.

Transmission of the tungro virus was lowest in Gampai 30-12-15, Habiganj DW8, and Ambemohar 159, although these varieties were as susceptible to the hopper as TN1, based on life span.

Insect life spans ranged from 1 to 39 days, with an average of 7 days (7.5 for females and 6 for males). The short life spans on Pankhari 203 and Ptb 18 indicated that these varieties were more resistant than the others in the test. ■

Rice insect pests in Vietnam

Nguyen Cong That, Entomology Department, Institute of Plant Protection, Hanoi, Vietnam

The pattern of incidence of insect pests in Vietnam has changed considerably since the introduction of high-yielding rice varieties and accompanying technology in 1968. Several minor insect pests have become major economic factors (see table).